

Experimental Integration of Non-5G Capable Devices into 5G Networks via Untrusted WLAN: the UNIF Approach

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Abstract— This paper introduces the Untrusted Non-3GPP Interworking Function (UNIF), a novel network function designed to enable devices that do not support the 5G NAS protocol over untrusted non-3GPP access networks to seamlessly connect to a 5G core network. Such devices are referred to as Non-5G Capable over Non-3GPP (N5CN3) devices. UNIF bridges a significant gap in current 3GPP specifications by allowing such devices to utilize untrusted non-3GPP access networks, such as public WLANs, for 5G connectivity. The prototype implementation of UNIF supports single or dual Packet Data Unit (PDU) Sessions per N5CN3 device and dynamic traffic routing for edge and remote data networks. Evaluation results show that UNIF achieves an average connection setup time of 284ms, downlink throughput of 552 Mbps, and low latency of 18–35 ms, validating its potential to extend 5G to N5CN3 devices.

Keywords— 5G access via Untrusted WLAN, Untrusted Non-3GPP Interworking Function, Edge Computing, Traffic Influence.

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of advanced 5G networks has revolutionized connectivity by offering very high data rates, ultra-low latency, and support for massive device deployments. While 5G networks were designed to integrate both 3GPP and non-3GPP access networks, current 3GPP specifications primarily focus on enabling devices that support the 5G Non-Access Stratum (NAS) protocol over these access networks. To address the connectivity challenges faced by devices that do not support the NAS protocol over Wireless Local Area Network (WLAN), 3GPP introduced the Trusted WLAN Interworking Function (TWIF). The TWIF enables such devices to connect to the 5G core network by acting as an intermediary, facilitating authentication, registration, and PDU session establishment.

However, the TWIF is limited to devices connected to trusted WLAN access networks, as defined by 3GPP specifications. It cannot support devices relying on untrusted non-3GPP access networks, such as public Wi-Fi hotspots commonly found in airports, malls, or coffee shops. This restriction creates a significant gap, as many practical scenarios involve devices depending on untrusted access networks for connectivity.

To address this gap, this paper introduces the Untrusted Non-3GPP Interworking Function (UNIF), a novel network function that enables Non-5G Capable over Non-3GPP

(N5CN3) devices to securely connect to the 5G core network via untrusted non-3GPP access networks. UNIF establishes a secure communication channel using Virtual Private Network (VPN) technology and dynamically emulates User Equipment (UE) to interface with the 5G core. Furthermore, UNIF supports dual Packet Data Unit (PDU) sessions, enabling efficient traffic routing between edge and remote data networks. This capability leverages 5G's distributed architecture to deliver low-latency and high-throughput services tailored to diverse application requirements.

We have developed a prototype implementation of UNIF using OpenVPN [1] and UERANSIM [2] and have integrated it with Open5GS as the 5G core. Evaluation results demonstrate the feasibility and scalability of UNIF, showcasing performance metrics such as high throughput, low latency, and effective traffic distribution across edge and remote networks. These findings underscore the potential of UNIF to extend the reach of 5G services to a broader range of devices and scenarios.

Recent studies have explored the integration of non-3GPP access networks into 5G systems. For instance, Lemes et al. [3] provide a comprehensive overview of both trusted and untrusted non-3GPP accesses in 5G, detailing authentication procedures and data session establishments. Their work includes a practical implementation of untrusted non-3GPP access using WLAN, offering insights into performance metrics such as session establishment time and protocol overhead. Similarly, the Wireless Broadband Alliance's paper [4] analyzes various approaches for integrating WLANs into 5G networks, discussing solutions that range from core-centric techniques to those utilizing IETF-defined multi-path protocols. These studies highlight the ongoing efforts to unify diverse access technologies within the 5G framework, addressing challenges related to security, performance, and seamless user experience.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II presents the related background, including the limitations of existing solutions. Section III describes the architecture and operation of UNIF. Section IV details the experimental setup and presents evaluation results. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and outlines potential directions for future research.

Fig. 1. Connecting to 5GC via non-3GPP access networks

II. CONNECTING TO 5G CORE VIA NON-3GPP ACCESS NETWORKS

Fig. 1 illustrates the various methods by which devices can connect to a 5G core network through different types of non-3GPP access networks. These methods depend on both the device's capability to support the 5G NAS protocol and the trust level of the access network:

- **Untrusted Non-3GPP Access with 5G NAS Support:** Devices that support the 5G NAS protocol over non-3GPP access can connect to the 5GC through untrusted non-3GPP access networks via the Non-3GPP Interworking Function (N3IWF). The N3IWF provides a secure VPN-like function that relays NAS signaling and user-plane traffic between the device and 5GC and is extensively specified in 3GPP specifications (see [5], [6]). The mutual authentication between the device and 5GC relies on

Universal Subscriber Identity Module (USIM) credentials.

- **Trusted Non-3GPP Access with 5G NAS Support:** Devices capable of supporting the 5G NAS protocol over non-3GPP access can connect to the 5GC through trusted non-3GPP access networks via the Trusted Non-3GPP Gateway Function (TNGF). The TNGF ensures secure integration with the 5GC and is extensively specified in 3GPP specifications (see [5], [6]). Again, the mutual authentication between the device and 5GC requires USIM credentials.

- **Trusted Non-3GPP Access without 5G NAS Support:** Devices that *cannot* support the 5G NAS protocol over non-3GPP access, can connect to 5GC via the Trusted WLAN Interworking Function (TWIF), which is also specified in 3GPP specifications (see [5], [6]). Although TWIF was specified mainly for WLAN access networks, it is applicable to other types of trusted non-3GPP access networks. The TWIF acts as an intermediary, facilitating registration and PDU Session establishment with the 5GC on behalf of the device. In this scenario, although the device

cannot exchange NAS signaling with 5GC, it is required to possess USIM credentials. Extensible Authentication Protocol (EAP)-based mutual authentication takes place between the device and the Authentication Server Function (AUSF) in 5GC.

- **Untrusted Non-3GPP Access without 5G NAS Support:** This scenario represents a gap in current 3GPP specifications. Devices lacking 5G NAS support that connect to *untrusted* non-3GPP access networks (e.g., public WLANs at shopping malls, coffee shops, airports, etc.) cannot access the 5GC. This paper introduces the UNIF, a novel network function designed to fill this gap by enabling such devices to securely connect to the 5GC and utilize its services. UNIF acts as secure VPN gateway, facilitating registration and PDU Session establishment with the 5GC on behalf of the device. More details are specified in section III.

The figure underscores the need for the UNIF to extend 5G

Fig. 2. UNIF functional components and operation.

connectivity to scenarios involving untrusted non-3GPP access networks, thereby broadening the applicability and utility of 5G networks.

III. PROPOSED SOLUTION: UNIF

In this section we introduce an innovative solution to bridge the connectivity gap identified in the previous section: enabling devices that are not capable of supporting the 5G NAS protocol over non-3GPP access networks to connect to a 5G core network via *untrusted* non-3GPP access networks.

We refer to the devices that are not capable of supporting the 5G NAS protocol over non-3GPP access networks as "Non-5G Capable over Non-3GPP access" (N5CN3) devices.

The solution lies in the development of a novel network function, referred to as *Untrusted Non-3GPP Interworking Function* (UNIF), which allows N5CN3 devices to establish a secure and reliable connection to a 5G core network through commonly available untrusted non-3GPP access points (e.g., public WLAN hotspots). This function acts as an intermediary, initiating a 5G registration and PDU Session establishment procedure on behalf of each N5CN3 device that connects to it. Further details are presented below.

A. Prototype Design and Implementation

Fig. 2 illustrates the key functional components and the operation of UNIF and its interaction with N5CN3 devices. The main function of UNIF is to create an emulated UE instance for each connected N5CN3 device, enabling seamless integration into the 5G core network. The key functional components of UNIF are presented below:

The VPN server facilitates secure connections from N5CN3 devices over untrusted non-3GPP access networks. It manages the establishment of VPN tunnels (e.g., VPN Tunnel-0 and VPN Tunnel-1) with N5CN3 devices and uses Network Address Translation (NAT) to manage IP address allocation and routing within UNIF. Mutual authentication takes place during the VPN connection establishment based on digital certificates provisioned in the devices and in the VPN server. In our implementation, we chose to apply certificate-based authentication over USIM-based authentication in order to support a wide range of devices, even simple IoT sensors without USIM support.

The UNIF Application (UNIF app) is the central control component that manages the creation and lifecycle of emulated UE instances. It monitors the VPN server and detects when a N5CN3 device attempts to establish a VPN connection. After it successfully authenticates with the VPN server, it instantiates a new emulated UE based on the Client Id presented by the authenticated N5CN3 device. Subsequently, it detects when the emulated UE successfully registers with 5GC and establishes a PDU Session and creates IP routing rules to forward the traffic from the VPN connection to the associated PDU Session and vice versa. When the VPN tunnel of the N5CN3 device is terminated, the UNIF app terminates also the associated emulated UE and its PDU Session. As shown in Fig. 1, after a PDU Session is established an associated virtual network interface is created in UNIF (see `uesimtun0`, `uesimtun1`).

Each emulated UE supported in UNIF must have pre-defined configuration data, which is stored in the UE configuration datastore. For each emulated UE the datastore

contains information such as the Client Id of the associated N5CN3 device, authentication keys, slicing information, subscriber identity, and other information needed for 5G registration, as well as PDU Session data, including DNN, SSC mode, slice selection identities (S-NSSIs), etc. As shown in Fig. 2, the VPN tunnel of each N5CN3 device is bound to the virtual network interface of the PDU Session established by the associated emulated UE.

The emulated UEs as well and the emulated gNB within UNIF are based on the open-source UERANSIM tool [2], which is designed to emulate the functionality of UE and gNB components. It provides a robust platform for testing and developing 5G access systems by simulating real-world network scenarios and interactions with 5G core networks. The communication between the emulated UEs and the emulated gNB takes place over the internal UDP/IP network of UNIF.

The IP layer in UNIF is configured by the UNIF app with appropriate routing policy that handles the routing and forwarding of data packets between the VPN tunnels and their associated PDU sessions, each one created by an emulated UE.

The emulated gNB in UNIF supports the standard N2/N3 interfaces for connecting with a 5G Core Network (5GC). In our testbed we used Open5GS [7] as an open-source implementation of 5GC, which complies with 3GPP standards and supports functionality such as user authentication, session management, and data routing. However, UNIF can interface with any other type of 5GC implementation.

By incorporating the above components, UNIF provides a robust and scalable solution for connecting N5CN3 devices to the 5G core, ensuring seamless service delivery and compatibility with existing 5G network standards.

B. N5CN3 Device Connection Procedure

Fig. 3 illustrates the detailed procedure for connecting a Non-5G Capable over Non-3GPP Access (N5CN3) device to a 5G core network via UNIF. The process is described step by step as follows:

- (1) The N5CN3 device connects to an untrusted non-3GPP access network and obtains IP connectivity, i.e., it receives IP configuration data including an IP address.
- (2) The N5CN3 device discovers the IP address of a UNIF that can provide 5G connectivity to a specific Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN). The N5CN3 device is assumed to be configured with the identity of the PLMN, i.e., Mobile Country Code/Mobile Network Code (MCC/MNC).

To discover the IP address of UNIF, the device typically uses the Domain Name System (DNS) and transmits a DNS query. For example, the device transmits a DNS query to resolve the domain name: `"UNIF.5gc.mnc<MNC>.mcc<MCC>.pub.3gppnetwork.org"`, where the MCC, MNC is the identity of the specific PLMN.

Alternatively, if the device supports *also* 3GPP access (e.g., 5G NR access) and is registered to the same PLMN through 3GPP access, the device may attempt to discover a UNIF near to its present location area. A UNIF deployed near to the location area of the device can typically provide better communication quality, e.g., reduced latency and packet error rate. In this case, the

device would transmit a DNS query to resolve the domain name:

"tac-lb<TAC-low-byte>.tac-hb<TAC-high-byte>.tac.UNIF.5gc.mnc<MNC>.mcc<MCC>.pub.3gppnetwork.org", where the TAC-low-byte and the TAC-high-byte indicate the Tracking Area Code (TAC) of the area which the device is register in via 3GPP access.

- (3) The N5CN3 device initiates a VPN connection to the discovered UNIF function. In our implementation we used OpenVPN, but any other VPN technology could be used, including e.g., IKEv2, TLS/SSL, etc. The VPN connection is terminated to the VPN server function in UNIF.
- (4) During the VPN connection establishment, an authentication procedure is triggered wherein the VPN server and the N5CN3 device are mutually authenticated. In our implementation, this authentication is based on pre-configured certificates which are exchanged between the VPN server and the device. We chose not to use USIM-based authentication since many N5CN3 devices cannot support USIM modules.
- (5) After the authentication is successfully executed, but before the VPN connection is fully established, the VPN server assigns a VPN address to the N5CN3 device and sends a connection request to the UNIF app, which includes a Client Id and the VPN address (client VPN address).
- (6) The UNIF app instantiates a new emulated UE, i.e., it creates a new process that emulates the operation of a UE.

As mentioned before, the UNIF is pre-configured with a list of emulated UEs, each one associated with a different Client Id. Each N5CN3 devices possesses a unique Client Id.

When the UNIF app receives the connection request, it selects to instantiate an emulated UE (out of the list of pre-configured emulated UEs) based on the received Client Id. Each emulated UE is associated with configuration data stored in the UE configuration datastore that specify the subscription data of the UE, such as its permanent subscription identity (SUPI), authentication credentials, default values for DNN, slices, etc.

Right after the emulated UE is instantiated, it initiates a standard 5G registration procedure with the 5GC, followed by a PDU Session establishment procedure. Both procedures are executed between the emulated UE and an AMF in 5GC via an access node, which supports the standard N2 interface. In our prototype implementation, the access node was an emulated gNB implemented inside the UNIF.

From the 5GC point of view, the UNIF in seen as initiating a 5G registration procedure and a PDU Session establishment procedure on behalf of the N5CN3 device. This behavior is like the behavior of TWIF specified in 3GPP TS 23.502 [6].

- (7) After the UNIF app instantiates the emulated UE, it monitors the operation of this UE and determines when the 5G registration and the PDU Session establishment are

Fig. 3. Procedure for connecting an N5CN3 device to 5G core.

completed. If they are successfully completed in a pre-configured time period, the UNIF app proceeds to the next step. Otherwise, it sends a Connection Rejected response to the VPN server, which then rejects the VPN connection with the N5CN3 device.

- (8) Once the UNIF app determines that the PDU session is successfully established, it determines the name of the created network interface (e.g. uesimtun0) and configures the IP layer so that it routes all traffic from the "Client VPN address" of the N5CN3 device via the established PDU session. This kind of routing ensures that all uplink traffic received from the N5CN3 device is sent through the established PDU Session and all downlink traffic received from the PDU Session is forwarded to the N5CN3 device. Note that the UNIF can simultaneously support many N5CN3 devices, each one associated with a different emulated UE and with a different PDU Session.
- (9) After the UNIF successfully configures its IP layer, it sends a Connection Accepted message to VPN server, which then completes the VPN connection with the N5CN3 device. This finalizes the VPN connection establishment and the association of the VPN connection with a PDU Session towards the 5G core network.
- (10) After the N5CN3 device successfully establishes the VPN connection, it starts sending IP packets via this VPN connection. As previously mentioned, all these IP packets are forwarded by the IP layer in UNIF to the PDU session associated with the N5CN3 device and vice versa.

The above procedure highlights the seamless integration of N5CN3 devices into the 5G ecosystem through the innovative capabilities of UNIF.

C. Support of multiple PDU Sessions

In many scenarios, such as those considered in the context of the HORIZON-JU-SNS-2023 EU project *ENVELOPE*, there is need for a N5CN3 device to simultaneously access data services deployed in a remote data network *and* data services deployed in an edge data network.

Our UNIF implementation can support such scenarios as

demonstrated in Fig. 4. When the N5CN3 device connects to the VPN server in UNIF, the UNIF app creates two emulated UEs (e.g., UE-0 and UE-1). Each emulated UE is assigned to establish a PDU session to a specific data network. For instance, UE-0 is configured for the remote data network, while UE-1 is configured for the edge data network. Both emulated UEs register with the 5G core and establish their respective PDU sessions as explained before.

The UNIF app configures the IP layer with a routing policy that directs traffic based on the target data network. Traffic destined for the edge data network is routed through the PDU session associated with UE-1, while other traffic is routed through the PDU session associated with UE-0 for the remote data network.

The routing policy can be pre-configured in the UNIF or can dynamically be provided by a vertical application using the Traffic Influence API exposed by the NEF in the 5G core. This API allows the vertical application to specify traffic criteria, such as IP addresses and/or protocols, that should be routed to the edge data network. After receiving these traffic criteria, the NEF forwards them to UNIF app, which translates them into routing rules at the IP layer, ensuring that the traffic is dynamically directed to the appropriate PDU session. The configured routing policy ensures that selected traffic, such as requests to edge application servers, is handled by the local UPF and directed to the edge data network, while other traffic is forwarded to the remote UPF for delivery to the remote data network.

Note that, since Open5GS does not currently support the NEF function, the NEF shown in Fig. 4 is a custom add-on component that exposes the Traffic Influence API but interacts directly with UNIF, not SMF. This enables us to support the Traffic Influence API in an Open5GS-based network but with no impact to the Open5GS implementation.

By supporting dual PDU sessions and dynamic routing policies, UNIF enables efficient use of 5G's distributed architecture, ensuring that latency-sensitive applications are served by the edge while other data needs are met by remote networks.

Fig. 4. Multiple PDU Sessions enabling simultaneous access to edge and remote data networks.

IV. EVALUATION AND RESULTS

The prototype implementation of UNIF was evaluated in a controlled testbed environment. The testbed setup included the following:

- UNIF implemented on a Linux server running Ubuntu 22.04 LTS, with Intel Core i7 (8 cores, hyper-threading), 64 GB DDR4 RAM, 512 GB NVMe SSD, 1 Gbps Ethernet.
- Open5GS deployed in a single VM including the 5GC control-plane elements (AMF, SMF, PCF, etc.) and the remote UPF.
- A WAN link between UNIF and Open5GS was simulated using the Netem [8] tool, which supports bandwidth adjustment, delay, jitter and packet loss.
- A local UPF deployed in another VM located in the same local area network as the UNIF server, providing low-latency connectivity to an edge data network.
- Multiple N5CN3 devices connecting to UNIF via a private WiFi-6 (IEEE 802.11ax) access network and a backhaul link of 1Gbps. Each N5CN3 device was deployed in a docker container running an OpenVPN client and iPerf for traffic generation.

The evaluation focused on key performance metrics, which are summarized in Table 1.

TABLE I. PERFORMANCE METRICS FOR THE UNIF PROTOTYPE

Performance Metric	Result
Average N5CN3 connection setup time	284ms, including PDU Session establishment of 162ms
Throughput	Downlink: 552 Mbps, Uplink: 363 Mbps for a single N5CN3 device to access the edge data network.
Latency	Edge Traffic: 18 ms, Remote Traffic: 35 ms
CPU Utilization	45% (15 devices), 78% (30 devices) Each device downloading a 10Mbps stream
Dual PDU Session Handling	Routing Reconfiguration Time: 83 ms

The evaluation results demonstrate that the UNIF prototype effectively addresses the gap in enabling N5CN3 devices to connect to a 5G core network via untrusted non-3GPP access networks. The prototype showcased high throughput and low latency, although the softwarized local UPF is deemed to impact the performance considerably. We believe that with some software optimizations (especially in the design of UNIF app) these metrics will reach much better values and the CPU utilization will be improved. With 30 devices, CPU usage reached 78%. Future work will investigate load balancing and horizontal scaling. Additionally, the dual PDU session functionality and its integration with the Traffic Influence API, was successfully demonstrated. This functionality highlights UNIF's potential for efficient traffic routing between edge and remote data networks, ensuring optimal performance for diverse applications.

These findings validate the feasibility of the proposed architecture, laying a strong foundation for future research and deployment in real-world scenarios.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduced the Untrusted Non-3GPP Interworking Function (UNIF), a novel solution to enable Non-5G Capable over Non-3GPP (N5CN3) devices to securely connect to a 5G core network via untrusted non-3GPP access networks. By bridging a significant gap in current 3GPP specifications, UNIF extends the reach of 5G services to scenarios where trusted access networks are unavailable, such as public Wi-Fi hotspots. The proposed architecture leverages VPN technology for secure communication and emulates UE to interface with the 5G core. Additionally, UNIF supports dual PDU sessions, allowing dynamic and efficient traffic routing between edge and remote data networks.

The prototype implementation of UNIF, based on OpenVPN and UERANSIM and integrated with Open5GS as the 5G core, demonstrated its feasibility and performance in a controlled testbed environment. Evaluation results highlighted UNIF's ability to achieve high throughput, low latency, and acceptable scalability for multiple simultaneous connections. These findings validate UNIF as a practical and effective solution for extending 5G capabilities to a broader range of devices and applications, particularly in IoT and public connectivity scenarios.

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